

**EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON ENHANCED OIL RECOVERY OF HEAVY
OIL USING NANOSILICA COMBINED WITH POLYMER FLOODING IN
A POROUS MEDIUM**

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project work on “**EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON ENHANCED OIL RECOVERY OF HEAVY OIL USING NANOSILICA COMBINED WITH POLYMER FLOODING IN A POROUS MEDIA**” was written by **ISO USANG USANG** with registration number **20151011493** under the supervision of **Engr. Dr. N.C. Izuwa**. It is my original work except for those areas referenced and no part of this work has been presented elsewhere for an award of any degree or certificate.

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DEDICATION

Firstly, this Project work is dedicated to God Almighty for His wisdom, immense grace, provision, sustenance and enablement throughout my undergraduate studies and my life in general. Also, this work is dedicated to my loving parents Rev & Dr. Mrs. Usang Iso, who has consistently and undoubtedly supported me throughout my undergraduate studies with the much needed support and encouragement in this great citadel of learning.

I also want to dedicate this project to myself for my persistence, hard work, and determination in surmounting every struggle of life. And finally to all students who are passionate about the oil and gas industry, may God see us through.

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ABSTRACT

It is no news that vital sources of non-renewable energy which are relevant to our daily use and consumption are severely being depleted in Nigeria and the world in general. As such, oil companies are turning to unconventional sources of non-renewable energy such as heavy oil and shale oil. Research also proves that Nigeria is blessed with over 30-40million barrels of heavy oil deposits in the south-Western region which lie unharnessed. Also, as we all evidently know, primary and secondary recovery methods of heavy oil are not sufficient enough to produce these large subsurface deposits of heavy oil and a tertiary/enhanced method is needed to fully and economically produce the oil.

These research work seeks to experimentally enhance the recovery of Heavy oil using Nanosilica (which was utilized in the form of silica powder) combined with a polymer flooding process in a porous medium. Major areas of focus include the behavior of the silica powder (nanosilica) on the polymer, the stability of the nanosilica in the reservoir, the effect of its particle sizes on Interfacial Tension, and the additional rate of recovery of the nanosilica.

In this research work, materials were obtained locally from the market and flooded in a core flooding experimental process, using a core flooding simulator. The results which were presented in a table showed that flooding with the polymer (PAM) resulted in a 21.43% increase in heavy oil recovery, flooding with the nanosilica resulted in a 6.25% increase in heavy oil recovery, while a 9.09% increase in heavy oil recovery was discovered upon flooding with a 50-50 blend of Polyacrylamides and silica powder. Carefully analysis of the results showed that the Polyacrylamides performed best in the core flooding process, rather than enhance the performance of the polyacrylamides, the silica powder inhibited its performance and was not stable in the porous medium. As a recommendation, an appropriate solvent should be found to dissolve the silica powder, or actual nanosilica in nano sizes used.

TABLE OF CONTENT

Title Page	i
Certification	ii
Dedication	iii
Acknowledgement	iv
Abstract	v
Table of content	vi
List of tables	viii
List of figures	ix
CHAPTER ONE	
1.0 Introduction	1
1.1 Background of study	2
1.1.1 Nanoparticles Technology	3
1.2 Statement of Problem	5
1.3 Aims and Objectives	6
1.4 Significance of Study	6
1.5 Scope and Limitations	6
CHAPTER TWO	
2.0 Literature Review	7
2.1 Primary Oil Recovery	7
2.2 Secondary Oil Recovery	7
2.2.1 water flooding	8
2.2.2 Gas injection	8
2.3 Tertiary/Enhanced Oil Recovery	9
2.3.1 Introduction	9

2.3.2	EOR Techniques for Heavy oil	9
2.3.3	Thermal EOR	10
2.3.4	Gas EOR	13
2.3.5	Chemical EOR	13
2.4	Polymer flooding	14
2.5	Nanosilica Particles and Technology	14
2.6	Empirical Literature	17
 CHAPTER THREE		
3.0	Materials and Methodology	23
3.1	Preparation of brine solution	24
3.2	Preparation of HPAM solution	25
3.3	Preparation of the nanosilica solution	25
3.4	Methodology	26
 CHAPTER FOUR		
4.0	result presentation and analysis	31
4.1	core flooding experimental result presentation	31
4.2	result analysis	31
4.3	observations/discussions	33
 CHAPTER FIVE		
5.1	Conclusion	34
5.2	Recommendation	34
	References	36

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.0: showing core rock properties	24
Table 3.1: showing fluid Properties at Ambient conditions	25
Table 3.2: showing fluid Properties at reservoir conditions	25
Table 4.1: showing core flooding experimental results	31

LIST OF FIGURES

Fig1: Nigeria bitumen belt	5
Figure 2.1: secondary oil recovery showing water/gas injection	20
Figure 2.2: Different EOR techniques	20
Figure 2.3: Combined CSS process with multiple wells	20
Figure 2.4: Schematic of SAGD/ISC hybrid recovery process.	21
Figure 2.5: chemical structures of (a) PAM and (b) HPAM	21
Figure 2.6: showing constituents of nanoparticles	21
Figure 2.7: SEM images for AEROSIL® 200 from Evonik Industries (2015).	22
Figure 2.8: nanoparticles as agent of wettability alteration.	22
Figure 3.0: Anton Paar Density Meter	23
Figure 3.1: Industrial salt	23
Figure 3.2: 25gm of polyacrylamide	23
Fig 3.3: showing dissolved PAM and silicon powder	24
Figure 3.4: soxhlet extractor	26
Figure 3.5: core cleaning procedure	26
Fig 3.6: schematic diagram of a core flooding set up	27
Figure 3.7: AFS 300 Core Flooding System	28
Figure 3.8: oil recovered by different EOR agents.	30
Fig 4.0: graph showing results of each EOR agent	33

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Vital sources of nonrenewable energy such as crude oil, natural gas, and gas condensate are pertinent to our daily use and consumption. Cars, Aero planes, ships, generators, industrial machines and even cooking gas all require one or more component of crude oil, otherwise called Petroleum. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA) and Energy central, world oil demand increased by 900kb/d to stand at 30.6 mb/d in 2019. With a yearly increase of ~1.3%, this is estimated to increase to over 121mb/d by the year 2040 due to population growth and industrialization. (EIA, 2020).

However, existing statistics shows disparities between demand and supply of this necessary fossil fuel. Specifically, OPEC- oil production decreased by 0.2% in 2018 following sharp declines in major oil-producing countries like Angola, Iran and Venezuela. Likewise, Nigeria, presently with an unstable daily production of ~2.1 million barrels of oil.

Besides the ever-increasing worldwide energy demands which indicates the need to increase oil recovery and production from natural reservoirs, conventional light oil production from natural reservoirs worldwide is on a steady decline, which calls for exploration of existing heavy oil reserves.

Experimental analogy shows that there are three major methods for EOR. These are 'primary', 'secondary' and 'tertiary' or enhanced oil recoveries. Primary recovery basically entails the production of subsurface hydrocarbons using in-built geological reservoir pressure. The Secondary recovery method further uses water flooding too, amongst others to boost reservoir pressure and has also been discovered to result in poor sweep recovery results of the heavy oil as a result of viscous fingering. In order to circumvent this problem, a Tertiary method of EOR was

proposed as a solution to declining oil production by use of polymer flooding since the early 1950's (Pye et al, 1964; Sandiford et al, 1964). These recovery techniques (Primary and Secondary) suffice to say are insufficient enough and can barely recover more than a third of the Original Oil in Place (OOIP).

The possibilities of enhancing heavy oil recovery through the introduction of technologies that are efficient and environmentally friendly, such as nanoparticles have recently been discovered. Nanotechnology is depicted by the application of materials in production designs and implementation at the nanometer (nm) scale. It has been projected at numerous times to be a forerunner or keystone of future energy technologies and could offer quality innovative solutions. (Serrano et al., 2009; Subbiah & Yun, 2010).

In Nigeria, the heavy oil reserves and bituminous sand deposits lie in a 12-km wide belt extending from Ijebu-ode in Ogun state, through Ondo, down till Edo state (see Fig 1 below). And according to Tetede (2006) the upper part of the cretaceous sequence of Abeokuta formation in the Eastern Dahomey Basin of Ogun state contains more than 40% of Nigeria's heavy oil reserves. The exploration of these tar sands containing heavy oil & bitumen deposits can result in over 30-40 million barrels of heavy oil deposits in South Western Nigeria (Ossai, 2016).

Different from conventional light crude, these crude types are normally depicted by their high density and viscosity in their original reservoir conditions, and as such, viscosity reduction (μ_0) and mobility increase (k/μ_0) are vital ways of recovering them effectively. Enhanced oil recovery (EOR) techniques are therefore employed to increase oil recovery by increasing mobility ratio and also having an effect on the properties of the porous media.

1.1 Background of study

Several research works have proven that between different materials used in EOR processes, polymers potentially increase the mobility ratio by increasing the injected fluid viscosity

and reducing the permeability of water phase (SA et al., 2010; Shi et al., 2010). In addition to polymers being effective, developments in Nanotechnology has proven that addition of effective nanoparticles in the polymer flooding process can also further improve the oil recovery factor (Maghzi et al., 2011; Maghzi et al., 2014).

During a comparative study by Cui and Babadagli (2017), in which they sought to determine the “mechanisms of conventional sulfonate surfactants and nanofluids for heavy oil recovery”, by using a glass micromodel to replicate sandstone formation, the study found out that nanofluids exhibited a different behavior from conventional surfactants, as an interface was created between the nanofluids and rock grains, which results in capillary inhibition thereby improving heavy oil recovery.

Nanoparticles/Nanofluids can be greatly used in EOR processes because in a formation, they upgrade recovery performance, and enhance heavy oil by acting as catalysts. Some mechanisms involved consists catalytic hydro cracking and wettability alteration, (the reservoir wettability also changes from an oil-wet condition to water-wet condition) (Karimi et al., 2012; Cao et al., 2017; Ajumobi et al., 2018). Nanoparticles also can be used to catalyze combustion in-situ process for heavy oil (Ossai, 2016).

1.1.1 NANOPARTICLES TECHNOLOGY

Recent studies by researchers in disciplines such as bio medicine, engineering, physics, chemistry, microbiology and so on have made ground breaking advances in the use of nanotechnology in the oil and gas industry, especially in EOR processes for heavy oil. Several nanoparticles of different sizes, types, unique concentrations have all been employed in many experiments. According to Xiaohu Dong et al., (2019), commonly used nanoparticles include various types of aluminum, aluminum oxide, copper, copper oxide, silica, cobalt, nickel. Specific

types of nanoparticles employed ideally in polymer flooding experiments also include; Al_2O_3 , TiO_2 and SiO_2 . Although, these nanoparticles may appear expensive, they ensure better recovery performance and produce more effective results especially in high temperature high pressure reservoirs (HTHP).

Karimi et al., (2012) in their study of Wettability alteration in carbonates using Zirconium oxide Nano fluids concluded that Zirconium oxide (ZrO_2) affects carbonate rocks by wettability alteration from strongly oil-wet to strongly water-wet nanofluids and so is rarely used in EOR. Researches have also highlighted that different chemical properties such as; rheology and magnetism, thermal stability, and high sedimentation which rely greatly on the shape and sizes of the nanoparticles contributes greatly to increase in EOR of the heavy oil.

Applications of nanoparticles in chemical EOR processes and studies prove that different methodologies poses significant opportunities in increasing recovery factor of heavy oil. Sharma et al., 2016 observed an evident increase of 8.71% (gotten from 15.97% to 24.68%) during the introduction of Nanosilica particles in surfactants (sodium dodecyl sulphate) polymer (polyacrylamide) in the flooding system.

Kumar et al., 2017 also observed a drastic reduction in the interfacial tension (IFT) and rheological enhancement due to synergy between the Nanosilica particles and carboxyl methyl cellulose polymers. Further studies also prove that the presence of nanoparticles lowers the viscosity of the heavy oil whilst also increasing its saturated hydrocarbon content.

These experimental studies illustrate that addition of Nanosilica (or silica nanoparticles SiNP's) combined with polymer-flooding process can boost oil recovery in heavy oil reservoirs while being environmentally friendly and of natural composition to sandstone oil reservoirs. Though, a lot of studies have been conducted for advanced countries, but few studies are in relation

to Nigeria. It is based on this that this study aims undertaking an experimental study to enhance oil recovery of heavy oil using Nanosilica combined with polymer flooding in a porous media.

Fig1: Nigeria bitumen belt

Source:www.researchgate.net

1.2 Statement of Problem

Nigeria as well as other world producers of crude oil faces the impending challenge of declining oil production, especially in its conventional oil reservoirs. Furthermore, it has been proven that about 30-40 million barrels of heavy crude oil deposits which cannot be recovered by traditional methods lie unharnessed in different parts of Nigeria.

If Nigeria is to meet up its increasing oil demands, then she needs to find a way to effectively and efficiently harness its heavy oil reserves.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

The aim of this study is to make an experimental study on enhanced oil recovery of heavy oil using nanosilica combined with polymer flooding in a porous media. Its objectives include;

1. To determine the behavioral effect of nanosilica on polymer flooding.
2. To determine the rate/potential of enhanced heavy oil recovery of nanosilica combined with polymer flooding in a porous media.
3. To determine the stability of nanosilica particles at reservoir conditions.
4. To determine the effect of nanoparticles crystallites sizes combined with polymer flooding on interfacial tension of heavy oil.

1.4 Significance of Study

Due to the rising economic situations in Nigeria, the need for improved crude oil production is pertinent. This experimental study will be of great benefit to the oil industry as it tackles the methods of enhancing oil recovery using Silica nanotechnology combined in a polymer-flooding process.

Its concrete and practical results will also serve as benefit to the academic institutions for further studies and addition to knowledge.

1.5 Scope and Limitations

In this project work, the area of great interest is on tertiary method of enhanced oil recovery with emphasis of addition of Nanosilica combined with polymer flooding. To be carried out in Laser Oil Laboratory, Port Harcourt.

Limitations to the research has not yet been encountered due to the fact that laboratory experiment has not yet been carried out.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 Literature Review

It can be said that successful crude oil recovery from subsurface reservoirs is at the heart of every oil production. Also, as earlier determined, daily production from these conventional reservoirs, is not sufficient enough to meet ever- increasing demands, hence the need for diversification from conventional light crude.

2.1 Primary Oil Recovery

Primarily, oil is recovered by using in-built geological reservoir pressure to lift hydrocarbons (oil, gas or condensate) to the surface by methodological application of pump jacks, and, or other lift devices. This technique is in many ways the first in the producing life of almost all reservoirs, especially in light crude, and is very limited in its extraction ability of the crude. Less than 5-15% of the well's potential and Original Oil In Place can be recovered by this method due to the gradual decline in reservoir pressure and natural drive mechanism, and oil production will gradually cease unless a secondary technique is applied to maintain reservoir energy. (see figure2.0).

2.2 Secondary Oil Recovery

As pressure decreases in the effective pore spaces of the reservoir during oil production, water (through water flooding process) and gas (through gas injection) is often times injected through injection wells to boost reservoir pressure and drive mechanism. This technique, known as secondary oil recovery is very popular in use and works by displacing the heavy crude (either with water, gas, steam or both) and filling the otherwise empty pore space (Muggeridge et al., 2014). Although, quite a number of factors must be considered such as oil and surrounding rock properties, spacing between the producer and injector wells, significant results proves that this

method can be efficient in recovering an additional 30% of the OOIP. This secondary method of oil recovery can also be done concurrently with the primary recovery method in order to avoid the reservoir crude reaching its bubble point early. (see figure 2.1.)

2.2.1 Water flooding

Water, is one of the cheapest and most abundant form of natural resources, it is widely used in different EOR processes including secondary oil recovery. Through direct injection in the pore spaces, water is flooded into the producing zone and density gradient between the crude and the water causes the crude to rise and flow into the producing wells. It is cheap and can be very effective, however determining factors such as reservoir geology, mobility ratio of the oil and water, distance between injectors and producers, and angle of injection, must all be considered during application.

2.2.2 Gas injection

Due to significant disparities in sedimentology and reservoir formations, gas, also is sometimes injected into the pore spaces of reservoir rocks instead of water. It works in quite a similar process with that of water flooding, except that unlike the water flooding process, the gas is injected into the gas cap through special gas injection wells.

Through exploitation of other methods (of EOR) other than reservoir pressure maintenance, like; water flooding, and gas injection, oil recovery can be boosted (Lake, 1989)

2.3 Tertiary/Enhanced Oil Recovery

2.3.1 Introduction

Oil recovery, especially when it includes EOR processes are usually related with the overall cost of production, and current oil price. Research studies have also shown that after the secondary phase of oil recovery, especially in heavy oil reservoirs, about 60-80% of the hydrocarbon is still left in the reservoir. EOR aims at producing as much oil as quickly as possible, which technically means having a high recovery factor (RF).

Primary, and secondary oil recovery techniques are known to follow a natural progression from the start to a point where it is no longer economical to produce from the reservoir (Sunil & Abdulaziz, 2010), and as such EOR processes are directly aimed at recovering over two-third of OOIP. As a result of this, methodological and strategic steps to recover oil (which may include; long-term commitments in both human and capital resources, advanced technologies up to microscopic and nanoscales) have been employed to produce positive results.

2.3.2 EOR Techniques for Heavy oil

According to Guo et al., (2016) in a comprehensive review on the pre-existing in-situ heavy oil recovery, EOR techniques can be broadly classified as; Thermal, Chemical & Gas injections. Before deciding on which EOR technique to employ, a number of criteria's are evaluated for optimal purposes, one of which includes the crude oil's density, where °API index is used as reference. Heavy crude which is the concern of this experiment is denoted by a large API. Another criteria is the cost of additives, water treatment, cost of facilities involved and so on.

2.3.2.1 Thermal EOR

According to Khan et al., (1992) Thermal recovery techniques for heavy oil first started in 1966 in Trintopec's operations with a small cyclic project. And even now, it is still one of the main exploitation technique for heavy oil and bitumen reserves currently in use. Thermal EOR is also the most employed EOR process (see figure 2.2). It is the most frequent and ideal technique when considering heating capacity and effect of steam and also serves as the most advanced EOR technique in terms of field experiences. Thermal EOR techniques are routinely applied in several heavy oil reservoirs around the world and even in the Niger Delta region, to reduce crude viscosity some of which include; Cyclic Steam Stimulation, Steam flooding and Steam Assisted Gravity Drainage etc (Farouq Ali, 1983; Kasraie & Farouq Ali, 1984). This in-situ frequently applied technology relies heavily on steam and has the least uncertainty in performance estimation due to its popularity in heavy oil EOR and oil sands technology (Speight James, 2009).

Common methods of heavy oil steam-based thermal recovery techniques which include steam injection includes;

- Cyclic Steam Simulation (CSS) otherwise called huff-and-puff (see figure 2.3).

A three-phase detailed operation stage spanning through several weeks, which begins with the steam injection for several weeks, then closely followed by a 3-5 days soaking period and finally a 10-100(s) days of oil producing period (Farouq Ali 2007; Liu, 2013). All of which is flexible and depends absolutely on the nature of the reservoir and its rock properties. The above mentioned phases make up a cycle and CSS cycles may span over 10 to 20 cycles per well. Importantly, CSS technique for heavy oil recoveries could include viscosity reduction, and heat swelling all of which eventually leads to solution gas driving. Its recovery factors are also within steam oil ratios (SOR)

of 3.0-5.22 and 20%-35% (Xiaohu Dong et al., 2019). Predominantly, it is practiced in vertical wells as conventional vertical well-based CSS technique (VW-CSS), but is now also being applied as horizontal well-based CSS technique (HW-CSS) because of considering factors like huge overburden and underburden heat losses, reduction in directional drilling costs, and improved sweep efficiencies in heavy oil reservoirs.

According to X. Dong et al., (2019) a major disadvantage in the conventional CSS process is that in its later stages, the thermal efficiency of steam drastically reduces and so a follow up process of recovery is required. Applications of this steam injection techniques are very popular in heavy oil reserves of Canada, Venezuela, Indonesia, and are being tried in countries like Brazil and China.

- Steam flooding and Steam Assisted Gravity Drainage (SAGD) (see figure 2.4).

Initially this method was suggested by Dr. Butler and his colleagues in 1980's (Butler RM, 1985;1987;1994). This seemingly complex process can be said to involve drilling two horizontal wells which are both 5-7m apart; in which one is placed at the top, acting as the steam injector and one at the bottom as the producer. At commencement of the startup or preheating phase (in which other thermal EOR processes, like CSS and Steam flooding can be employed here), a thermal connection is created between the producer and the injector and a steam chamber is created by steady injection from the top injector. Once the steam chamber reaches the reservoir top, a horizontal expansion is observed. Similarly, once the steam chamber approaches reservoir formation, it depletes and also, a reduction in the production rate of the oil (X. Dong et al., 2019). SAGD next and final phases may consist of the vertical and horizontal stages of expansion and exhaustion, in which the heated heavy oil and produced water flow downwards along the steam chamber boundary and are produced from the bottom producer well.

Unlike other thermal EOR techniques, the driving force of the oil drainage is gravity (X. Dong et al., 2019). Applications of SAGD processes are popular in heavy crude oil reserves of Canada and have been tested in Venezuela with limited reports of success, most SAGD worldwide techniques remain at field trials (Sunil Kolal, 2010).

- In-situ combustion (see figure 2.4)

Also known as fire flooding (Kumar, 1991; Guan, 2011), ISC is another vital technique used in the recovery of heavy oil and sand resources. Although not as popular as Steam flooding processes it has been reported in Canada, India and the US (Sunil Kolal, 2010) and entails placement of a heater or igniter into the injection well, and continuous injection of oxygen-rich air into the well, (and in some cases injection of water to reduce air requirements and steam). Several types of ISC processes include; Forward combustion (Dry and Wet), Reverse combustion and THAI (Toe to Heel Air Injection) (Butler 1991; Greaves et al., 2001; Ursenbach et al., 2010). Operation of the heater is done until ignition, then it is withdrawn and replaced with air to maintain combustion. The combustion reaction occurring in the surrounding rock provides enough heat to mobilize the heavy crude. ISC operates mainly under two features; Thermal cracking and Combustion gases, of which a combination of combustion gases, heavy-crude-made-light (produced as a result of thermal cracking), steam etc. results in the movement of heavy oil from the injector towards the producing wells. Temperature requirements of the combustion zone can reach up to 345-650°C (650-1200°F) (X. Dong et al., 2019). This technique is well suited as follow-up to the steam-based thermal techniques and can recover up to 80% of OOIP whilst partially improving in-situ crude density.

2.3.4 Gas EOR

Another popular EOR method applicable to heavy and light oil reservoirs is the gas injection. In simple terms, it involves the utilization of hydrocarbon gases (mostly alkanes) or non-hydrocarbon gases (especially CO₂) that has the capacity to dissolve in oil. It works by expansion of oil volume and reduction of oil viscosity. Usually, it is applied in light oil reservoirs in many parts of the world. In order to achieve complete miscibility in heavy oils, high pressure is required making the process quite difficult. Depending on the formation and gas type, gas EOR may be miscible or immiscible, with each of them proving different recovery mechanisms. Use of injected immiscible CO₂ into heavy oil reservoirs in some parts of USA, Turkey and Camurlu has been successful and since it is less expensive than liquefied petroleum gas, it has gained massive popularity.

2.3.5 Chemical EOR

In chemical EOR, the goal is to recover more oil by applying a series of numerous methods to enhance mobility control by addition of long chained molecules called polymers (in polymer flooding) to reduce mobility of injected water and reduce interfacial tension (ITF) using detergent-like alkali surfactants. More recently, nanoparticle technology is also used to reduce interfacial tension by prevention of oil droplets through the reservoir. Chemical EOR has been applied fundamentally in light oil reservoirs although recently, it is being applied to heavy oil reservoirs (Delamaide et al., 2014; Delamaide, 2014). Alvarado and Manrique (2010) names chemical EOR processes as the least applied of all EOR processes, and this can be attributed to factors such as sensitivity to the formation and surrounding rock, environmental and water safety, and cost of additives.

2.4 Polymer flooding

One of the prevalent Chemical Enhanced Oil Recovery (CEOR) methods used in EOR practices to boost oil production and area sweep deficiencies in reservoirs is the polymer flooding technique (Sheng 2011). However, this technique is susceptible to various hindrances such as polymer adsorption and thickening, mechanical degradation, presence of divalent cations amongst others, all of which has gravely impacted and limited its use.

Polyacrylamides (see figure 2.5), have in the past been the numera uno for CEOR of heavy crude operations because of existing better biological and chemical stabilities, cost of use and application and injection issues, when compared comparatively with other polymers (Holstein 2017). These polyacrylamide solutions when compared with ionic forms are less coagulating in their purest forms and are not well propagated through sand reservoirs. As a result of this thickening behavior, PAM is partially hydrolyzed (HPAM) in order to scatter the negatively charged groups along the polymer chain (Holstein 2017).

2.5 Nanosilica Particles and Technology

K. Aurand (2017) in her book Enhanced Oil Recovery using silica nanoparticles stated that the first specific published work involved in investigating hydrophilic nanoparticles as agents in EOR was conducted by Ju et al., in 2006. She noted that Ju's (2006) work was a follow-up of his past experiments which concluded that hydrophobic nanoscale polysilicon could alter wettability of porous surfaces (Ju et al., 2002) and since then, massive research studies have been carried out in nanoparticles, nanofluids, and enhancing the performance (and use) of polymers in EOR and in the petroleum sector. Majority of these research works in EOR were experimentally done.

In light of these, different approaches and reviews have risen up in regards to nanotechnology, for instance, Negin et al., (2016) talks on silica nanoparticles background for EOR while Bera and Belhaj (2016) and Sun et al., (2017) broadly discusses and compares proposed mechanisms for EOR and experiments on nanoparticles research.

Having expanded their work on nanotechnology applications, scientists have as a matter of fact established that appropriate addition of these nanoparticles in proportionate quantities will lead to improved performances like enhanced viscosity and rheology behaviors, increased thermal & chemical resistances and effective oil recoveries beyond what traditional polymer flooding can do. Silica nanoparticles which in this project interchanges as Nanosilica has been used frequently too because amongst others, it has a low-cost of fabrication and cost-surface modification.

Literature texts from Bera and Belhaj (2016) and Sun et al., (2017) suggested that nanosilica are the most frequently researched and applied nanoparticle type for EOR processes. Nevertheless, other types of nanoparticles such as metal oxides; aluminium dioxide, titanium dioxide and iron oxides have also been researched but will not be discussed in this project.

Metin et al., in 2012 after performing a study on comprehensive understanding of rheological behavior of these silica nanoparticles, came to a conclusion that the viscosity of dispersed nanosilica depends majorly on the concentration of this particles. Similarly, variations of shear and complex pores morphology between nanoparticles and their various tortuous flow channels affect viscosity of flow dispersion.

According to M. Zeyghami et al., (2014), Nanosilica augmentation has two distinguishing effects on polymer solutions. In sulfonated polyacrylamide solutions, it increases the viscosity while in hydrolyzed polyacrylamide solutions, it decreases viscosity when added in minuit quantities and

vice versa in large quantities. Also, by increase in concentration of existing electrolytes, effects of Nanosilica on viscosity is reduced and replaced with severe thickening (coagulation) problem.

- **Definitions and Terminologies**

Arce (2010) says that particle can be referred to as 'nano' when it is equal to or smaller than 100nm (1×10^{-7} metres) in at least one dimension. These particles (see figure 8) can come together to form many components which are; primary particles, aggregates and agglomerates (K. Aurand, 2017). The primary particles make up the structure of the nanoparticles and are the small individual constituents of the mixture. The aggregates are the binding parts of the nanoparticles and the agglomerates refers to an assembly of nanoparticles or aggregates (Nichols et al., 2002). This aggregates are not fused together but rather they are held together by weak inter-molecular forces such as van der waals forces or hydrogen bonds and can join together to form agglomerates (Evonik 2015).

Nanofluids also, can be termed as a solution containing nanoparticles (such as nanosilica) of either uniform or different sizes evenly suspended in a dispersing solution otherwise known as base solution. A basefluid filled with nanoparticles of an average size of 100 nanometres or less in constant colloidal suspension is termed a nanofluid (El-Daisty, 2013). These base fluids could vary from either water, brine or gas. In these experiment, nanofluids will be formed by adding various nanoparticles in water (or brine) to improve water flooding recovery with the help of polymers.

The purpose of this project is to make an experimental study on enhanced oil recovery of heavy oil using nanosilica combined with polymer flooding in a porous media.

2.6 Empirical Literature

When considering wettability alteration and viscosity change of the heavy oil in a porous medium we make reference to Van S.L et al in his (2016) publication; Chemical flooding in heavy-oil reservoirs from technical investigation to optimization using response surface methodology. Rock wettability is in simple terms the ability of a fluid amidst another immiscible fluid to adhere to the surface of a rock. Rock wettability is a governing factor in heavy oil recovery because of its prevalent effects on capillary pressure, fluid saturation and relative permeability, and it has been proved that nanofluids are agents of wettability alteration. (see figure 2.8).

Roustaei A & Bagherzadeh H. (2015) also in the same vain investigated experimentally, the impact of Nanosilica (SiO_2) on carbonate rocks wettability and agreed that nanosilica significantly alters carbonate rock wettability. Several authors also have different literature texts on nanofluids and their effect on wettability alteration of different rock types (sandstone, shale and carbobnate). This wettability alteration is denoted by several test methods like Amott tests and contact angle method (Giraldo et al, 2013).

Wettability alteration from oil-wet to water-wet is also observed in contact angle change between Nanosilica coated glass surfaces and heavy oils in different viscosities. Contact angle measurements of these heavy crude against Nanosilica fluids with various synthetic silica concentrations proves a direct proportionality between water wetness and concentration of nanoparticles (Maghzi et al, 2012).

When considering the effects of nanoparticles crystallites sizes combined with polymer flooding on interfacial tension of heavy oil, we realize that interfacial tension a vital parameter used in deciphering the movement and distribution of these nanofluids in a porous medium. As such,

obtaining the IFT between the heavy crude and the injected polymer fluids is important. Nanosilica in conjunction with polymer floodings are considered agents of IFT reductions.

Hendraningrat et al (2012;2013) conducted IFT measurements between nanofluids and synthetic oil and realized that by adding nanoparticles into brine, the IFT effect will be drastically reduced from 14.7mN/m to 9.3mN/m. Furthermore, when nanofluid concentration is increased from 0.01wt% to 0.05wt%, the IFT further decreases to 5.2mN/m, showing that IFT is sensitive to the nanoparticles crystallites concentration.

Li et al., 2013 and Parvazdavani et al., 2014 also carried out similar experiments on Nanosilica crystallite particles effects on IFT and inferred that the silica nanoparticles have a great impact on IFT reduction even than on wettability alteration.

Understanding the behavioral effect of nanosilica on polymer flooding shows us that the appropriate addition of nanoparticles in polymer flooding in a Nanoparticle assisted flooding process (especially in polyacrylamides: Maghzi et al., 2013) is done in order to boost and enhance performance, or in surfactant flooding (especially sodium dodecyl sulfate: Rahimi and Adibifard, 2015).

Determining the stability of nanosilica particles at reservoir conditions is characterized by nanoemulsions. These great indicators “nanoemulsions” of the overcoming ability of nanoparticles to withstand colloidal solids and surfactant induced challenges possess the ability to remain stable in the reservoir regardless of harsh conditions of high temperature high pressure, shear and salinity stresses. According to Binks and Binks (2005), nanoemulsions are relatively tiny and are able to penetrate through the pore spaces of rocks without retention, this aids in increasing their mobility ratio during flooding systems. Stability of these nanoemulsions at different reservoir conditions

according to Devendiran et al., (2016) - can be achieved through various methods including; Changing of PH value, Introduction of surfactants as a bridge between the nanoparticles and base fluids (Yu H. 2012), and Ultrasonic vibration technique in dispersing nanoparticles into base fluids (Nadler, 2008; Kavitha, 2012; Ruan et al, 2012). Usually stability of these nanoparticles dispersion in base fluids are identified by zeta potential values.

Determination of rate/potential of EOR of Nanosilica combined with Polymer flooding; in order to increase the reservoir rate of enhanced oil recovery of the heavy oil, vital guiding principles which may influence the dispersing process, an example of those factors include temperature of the nanoparticles, the base fluids and their injection time.

Figure 2.0: crude oil generation and production

Source: Wikipedia

Figure 2.1: secondary oil recovery showing water/gas injection

Source: Khan et al., (1992)

Figure 2.2: Different EOR techniques

Data from oil & gas journal, SPE, and other sources.

Figure 2.3: Combined CSS process with multiple wells: original crude oil, heated area, condensate steam zone.

Source: Xiaohu Dong et al., 2019 (Applied Energy journal).

Figure 2.4: Schematic of SAGD/ISC hybrid recovery process.

Source: Xiaohu Dong et al., 2019 (Applied Energy journal).

Figure 2.5: chemical structures of (a) PAM and (b) HPAM

Source: M. Zeyghami, R. Kharrat, and M. H. Ghazanfari (2014)

Figure 2.6: showing constituents of nanoparticles

Source: Enhanced oil recovery using silica nanoparticles by Katherine Aurand, 2017

Figure 2.7: SEM images for AEROSIL® 200 from Evonik Industries (2015).
 A) Agglomerates of the silica particles. B) A nano-structured particle (aggregate).
 Source: Enhanced oil recovery using silica nanoparticles by Katherine Aurand, 2017.

Figure 2.8: nanoparticles as agent of wettability alteration.

Source: Xiaofei Sun et al., 2017

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 Materials and Methodology

Materials. Different core plug samples from same depth with dimensions as shown in the table below was obtained from the Niger Delta sandstone formation and supplied by Laser Engineering & Resources Nigeria Limited. Heavy crude from the Niger Delta formation was also obtained and its fluid properties at room temperature measured using the Anton Paar DMA 500 Density Meter (see fig 3.0). Industrial salt (see fig 3.1) comprising mainly of NaCl was acquired from Joe Chemical Industries Limited, Port Harcourt. Polyacrylamides (see fig 3.2) was purchased from Chemical stores, Onitsha Market and then Hydrolyzed to form HPAM. Silica powder used as Nanosilica was also acquired from Chemical stores in Onitsha market.

Figure 3.0: Anton Paar Density Meter

Figure 3.1: Industrial salt

Figure 3.2: 25gm of polyacrylamides

ROCK PROPERTIES

Properties	PAM SAMPLE R&D1	SILICA POWDER SAMPLE R&D2	BLEND SAMPLE R&D3
Length (cm)	5.8	6.0	5.8
Diameter (cm)	3.4	3.8	3.4
Pore Volume (cm ³)	14.38	16.47	14.38
Bulk Volume (cm ³)	52.67	68.06	52.67
Porosity (%)	27.3	24.2	27.3
Permeability @5000psi (MilliDarcy)	501	490	501

Table 3.0: showing core rock properties

To Calculate Bulk Volume: $\pi d^2/4 * \text{Length of core.}$

To Calculate Pore Volume: wet weight – dry weight/ density of saturating fluid.

To Calculate Porosity: Pore Volume/ Bulk Volume * 100

3.1 Preparation of brine solution

30g of NaCl was measured into 1 liter of fresh water and then mixed thoroughly till the salt was completely dissolved inside (see figure 3.3). Fresh water was used instead of distilled water because in reservoir formations, fresh water is found there.

Fig 3.3: showing dissolved PAM and silicon powder

3.2 Preparation of HPAM solution

0.08wt% of the polyacrylamides was obtained by dissolving 0.8g of the polyacrylamides in the 100ml of brine solution and stirred completely till it was properly distributed (see figure 3.3).

3.3 Preparation of the nanosilica solution

0.5wt% of the nanosilica solution (see figure 3.3) was obtained by measuring 5g of the silica powder in 100ml distilled water and left for more than 3days in order to achieve as much solubility as possible.

FLUID PROPERTIES @ AMBIENT CONDITION ($T_{avg.} = 27^{\circ}C$)

Properties	Brine (3% NaCl)	Crude Oil	EOR Agent		
			0.08 wt. % PAM in 3wt. % NaCl	0.5 wt. % Silica	50:50 Blend of PAM and Silica
Specific Gravity	1.0199	0.9423	1.0180	1.0010	1.0124
Density (g/cm^3)	1.0167	0.9384	1.0143	0.9973	1.0087
Viscosity (cP)	0.91	124.06	3.94	0.88	0.81
API ($^{\circ}$) @ 15 $^{\circ}C$	-	17.91	-	-	-

Table 3.1: showing fluid Properties at Ambient conditions were obtained using the Anton Paar DMA 500 Density Meter and the Viscometer.

FLUID PROPERTIES @ RESERVOIR CONDITIONS (T = 50 $^{\circ}C$, P = 5,000psi)

Properties	Brine (3% NaCl)	Crude Oil	EOR Agent		
			0.08 wt. % PAM in 3wt. % NaCl	0.5 wt. % Silica Powder	50:50 Blend of PAM and Silica
Specific Gravity	1.0175	0.9335	1.0111	0.9993	1.0116
Density (g/cm^3)	1.0061	0.9235	1.0020	0.9906	1.0026
Viscosity (cP)	0.68	31.80	2.56	0.58	0.70
API ($^{\circ}$) @ 15 $^{\circ}C$	-	17.91	-	-	-

Table 3.2: showing fluid Properties at reservoir conditions were obtained using the Anton Paar DMA 500 Density Meter and the Viscometer.

3.4 Methodology

Core cleaning process

Upon obtaining the core samples, the Niger Delta sandstone cores were properly washed (and used for each of the core flooding process) using a laboratory procedure known as core cleaning, performed with a soxhlet extractor (see figure 3.4). The soxhlet extractor comprises of a heating mantle and glass wares (including a condenser). The core is first heated in 300ml of Toluene for 3hours to remove hydrocarbons left in it, then, it is heated in another mixture of 150ml each of toluene and methanol for another hour. The methanol is used to remove salt. Atmospheric drying of the core plug is then carried out to remove vapor content of the solvent which could ignite if immediately introduced to the oven, and finally oven drying till a constant dry weight is established. Core cleaning using toluene and methanol is a toxic process and so a respirator should be worn throughout the process (see figure 3.5).

Figure 3.4: soxhlet extractor

Figure 3.5: core cleaning procedure

Core flooding

Figure 3.6 illustrates the schematic diagram of a core flooding experimental set up and fig 19 illustrates the diagram of the core flooding simulator consisting mainly of the control system, control board and the heater in which the core holder is placed inside. (Make is AFS 300 Core Flooding System). The core flooding system is operated using a software known as smartflood and the instrument is controlled by hydraulic pressure (in this case water). Some important features inside the heater include the accumulators also known as test chambers where fluid (heavy oil and brine) were put inside and used in the flooding process.

Fig 3.6: schematic diagram of a core flooding set up

Figure 3.7: AFS 300 Core Flooding System

Experimental workflow procedures in Enhanced oil recovery using the core flooding process

- Determination of the rock properties of the sample.
- Saturation of the core plug samples with brine at 50°C and 5000psi.
- Drainage of the core samples with crude to determine the initial oil in place (OOIP).
- Carrying out the Imbibition study/water flooding to determine the residual oil (S_{or}).
- Injection of EOR agent (HPAM, Nanosilica and HPAM with Nanosilica).
- Evaluation of the additional recovery factor and displacement efficiency.

Step by Step Analysis of the core flooding process (using AFS 300 Core flooding system)

- An inlet end-stem gets in contact with the core plug and drives the plug firmly into the core sleep. The core sleep is then placed from the right properly in the core holder in order to avoid fluid by-pass.
- The outlet end-stem is inserted in the other end of the core plug and properly placed to ensure that the stem touches the core plug inside the core sleep. Both threads of the inlet and outlet are properly lubricated to avoid friction which could damage the core holder.

- The core holder is then placed inside the core flooding system heater and the overburden pressure lines at the top & bottom attached to it.
- Temperature probes are connected to the core holder and its temperature recorded to be 27°C (room temperature).
- Using overburden pump, and water as the hydraulic fluid, the overburden pressure is set to 1895psig and then built to 5000 psig imitating the reservoir pressure conditions.
- Brine and heavy crude are put into the accumulators or test chambers, and the differential pressure lines checked to ensure smooth flow into the core holder.
- The core in the core holder is then saturated with brine for over three hours to ensure complete and uniform saturation.
- Drain or de-saturate the core with oil to obtain the original oil in place in a closed system.
- Clean the core plug sample to remove every amount of oil inside.
- The core sample is then saturated with heavy oil for another three hours and more to ensure complete and uniform saturation.
- Secondary oil recovery is then initiated by using a water flooding process to displace the oil at a flowrate of 1ml/min (flowing with a higher rate than 1ml/min will trigger and move fines in the core sample which will alter core porosity and permeability).
- 20mins into the water flooding process, viscous fingering starts and after 2½ hours, the process is stopped when there was no further increase in the volume of oil collected. The collected crude is measured and recorded as the volume of crude received after water flooding.
- EOR flooding is then carried out in three (3) different stages using PAM, silica powder and a 50:50 blend of PAM & silica powder all in order to carefully observe the effects of each

agent. At a flowrate of 1ml/min again, each of the EOR agents is used to flood the core in order to recover more of the oil that could not be recovered using secondary recovery. The recovered oil is then collected with different cylinders and recorded as the volume of crude recovered after EOR agent (see figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8: oil recovered by different EOR agents.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULT PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 CORE FLOODING EXPERIMENTAL RESULT PRESENTATION

S/N	Parameter	Sample (PAM)	Sample (SILICA POWDER)	Sample (BLEND – PAM+SILICA POWDER)
1	Pore Volume (cm ³)	14.38	16.47	14.38
2	Volume of crude in the plugs (OOIP) at S _{wi} (cm ³)	14	16	11
3	Volume of water remaining in the plug samples at maximum oil saturation/ connate water (cm ³)	0.38	0.47	3.34
4	Initial water saturation (S _{wi}) – %	2.64	2.85	23.23
5	Initial oil saturation (%)	97.36	97.15	76.77
6	Volume of crude received (cm ³) after Imbibition (Waterflooding)	10	10	8
7	Volume of residual crude left over in the sample (cm ³)	4	6	3
8	Residual oil saturation (S _{or}) – (%)	28.57	37.50	27.27
9	Volume of crude received (cm ³) after Tertiary recovery	3	1	1
10	Additional Recovery (%) with EOR agents	21.43	6.25	9.09

Table 4.1: showing core flooding experimental results

4.2 RESULT ANALYSIS:

➤ PORE VOLUME:

To obtain the pore volume mathematically, we use wet weight – dry weight/density of saturating fluid.

➤ VOLUME OF CRUDE IN PLUG (OOIP):

To obtain the recoverable volume of crude in the plug experimentally, we displace the saturated brine from the core plug in a drainage process.

➤ VOLUME OF WATER IN THE PLUG SAMPLE:

The volume of the water remaining in the plug samples at maximum oil saturation is gotten by subtracting the volume of original crude in the plug from the pore volume.

➤ INITIAL WATER SATURATION:

Initial water saturation (S_{wi}) is the irrecoverable volume of water remaining in the plug divided by the pore volume, and can be expressed as a percentile by multiplying times 100.

➤ INITIAL OIL SATURATION:

Initial oil saturation is the recoverable volume of crude in the plug divided by the pore volume and expressed in percentage.

➤ VOLUME OF CRUDE RECEIVED AFTER IMBIBITION:

After water flooding, you obtain another volume of crude gotten from secondary EOR. This adds and makes up the total recoverable oil.

➤ VOLUME OF RESIDUAL CRUDE LEFT IN THE SAMPLE:

The volume of the residual amount of crude left in the core is gotten by subtracting the recovered volume of crude obtained by water flooding from the total amount of recoverable oil.

➤ RESIDUAL OIL SATURATION:

To obtain its saturation, you divide the volume of residual crude by the total amount of recoverable oil, and multiply by 100 to express it in percentile.

➤ VOLUME OF CRUDE RECEIVED AFTER TERTIARY RECOVERY:

After EOR flooding, another volume of crude is obtained and expressed in percentage.

Fig 4.0: graph showing results of each EOR agent

4.3 OBSERVATIONS/DISCUSSIONS

During the experiment, it was observed that the Silica powder was not completely soluble in distilled water. Although the mixture was left for several days to ensure maximum solubility, optimally, the silica powder did not dissolve properly.

Also, it was observed that the metallic oxide; (Silica powder) inhibited the performance of the Polyacrylamide as EOR agent during the blend of the two chemicals.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.1 CONCLUSION:

- From the experimental results above, we can infer that the behavioural effect of silica powder in polymer flooding results in inhibition of the polymer.
- The rate of enhanced oil recovery of nanosilica combined with polymer flooding is 9.09% as recorded above.
- Silica powder particles did not achieve complete stability as they could not properly dissolve in the solvent.
- As can be seen from the results above, the polymer (Polyacrylamide) performed best in enhancing the heavy oil recovery among the EOR agents used for this research.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION:

- In future, more research should be done to find out the appropriate solvent that can completely dissolve the metallic powder (Silica) in order to achieve complete stability.
- Actual nanoparticles in nano sizes should be used in preference to silica powder in EOR flooding.

PHOTO SPLASH

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